

Estimation of tea polyphenols by electrochemical sensors via ferric chloride modified electrodes

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Abstract : The present work reports unique electrochemical sensors for detection of polyphenols in tea infusion using ferric chloride as a modifier on glassy carbon, platinum and screen-printed carbon electrodes. The methodology involved reduction of ferric chloride (FeCl_3) to ferrous chloride (FeCl_2) with simultaneous oxidation of alcohols to aldehyde or ketone through one-electron-transfer mechanism. Amperometric responses were observed using working electrodes immobilized with ferric chloride. Various grades of tea produced consistent concentration pattern distinguishing green tea from black and other varieties. The method exhibited low limit of detection (0.192–0.318 mg/L), excellent selectivity against interfering compounds and required only five minutes for detection. The stability of the sensor was also very high due to use of inorganic salt. The other sophisticated techniques such as high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) require elaborate sample preparation, trained personnel and costly instrument. The technique proposed in this manuscript would serve as an attractive alternative due to minimal sample preparation, high selectivity, very fast sensing and low cost per analysis in comparison with HPLC and other methods. This method could be used to measure polyphenols quantitatively in terms of catechin and thus should have high importance to the customers as well as tea producers.

Keywords : Polyphenols, ferric chloride, amperometry, electrochemistry.

Introduction

Tea is one of the most popular drinks all over the world. The quality of tea can be judged by the polyphenols content of tea leaves which is around 30% of phenolic compound on the dry weight basis¹. Due to the presence of polyphenols in tea the taste of tea is slight astringent and bitter². The antioxidant properties of polyphenols make them scavenge free radicals which are generated by different metabolic pathways in our body³. Therefore, it is important to know content of total polyphenols in tea for our health benefit.

Amongst various grades of tea, green tea mainly consists of monomeric phenolic compounds like (–)-epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), (–)-epigallocatechin (EGC), (–)-epicatechingallate (ECG) and (–)-epicatechin (EC)^{4–6}. But black tea contains theaflavin (TF) and thearubigins (TR) due to oxidation of catechin during fermentation of tea leaves. Different types of volatile compounds (such as linalool, geraniol, nerolidol, benzaldehyde etc.) are responsible for flavor of tea whereas colour and taste of tea depends upon the components of liquor

like total phenolic compounds (EC, ECG, EGC, EGCG, TF, TR), caffeine etc.⁷.

Concentration of polyphenols in tea can be determined by some conventional technique such as high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) combined with UV-Vis detection, spectrophotometric detection, fluorescence detection, chemiluminescence detection⁸. Among these methods the spectrophotometric detection by Folin-Ciocalteu is the simplest. However the main drawbacks of this method are lengthy procedure of sample preparation e.g. solid phase extraction of polyphenols, interference by several substances, such as sugars, aromatic amines, sulfur dioxide, ascorbic acid, organic acids as well as nonphenolic organic substances that react with the reagent⁹. The method using HPLC is an authentic method but it needs costly equipment, elaborate sample preparation, complex operation and most importantly needs costly standard polyphenols to evaluate presence of each separately. It is also difficult to detect coelution (two compounds escaping from the tubing at once) with HPLC, which may lend to inaccurate compound categorization

specially for polyphenols. The detection of polyphenols by fluorescence spectroscopy is limited because the assay is costly and needs detection of each polyphenols separately¹⁰. The method by chemiluminescence measures the light emitted due to the reaction of the reagent and analyte and in the case of polyphenols detection, the components of the sample are first separated by HPLC and the inhibition of chemiluminescence of standard reagents such as luminol-potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) is measured for each of them¹¹.

Though the method is ultra sensitive, the procedure is more complex than HPLC and costlier and also not suitable for high concentration of polyphenols in tea.

Electroanalytical techniques can be used obtain quantity of polyphenols since these possess electrochemical properties. Some researchers have tried developing biosensors using enzymes tyrosinase, laccase, peroxidase etc.¹²⁻¹⁴. However, these biosensors using degradable biomaterials are not stable and use is restricted.

In this work, we have reported a simple detection procedure for polyphenols in tea infusion using a very common laboratory chemical i.e. iron(III) chloride (FeCl_3), also called ferric chloride. In this electrochemical assay, FeCl_3 is reduced to FeCl_2 whereas it oxidizes alcohols (polyphenols) to aldehydes or ketones (quinones) through one-electron-transfer mechanisms¹⁵. As compared to the above conventional techniques, the proposed method is simple, does not require any sample preparation, easy to use and can be conveniently employed in laboratory and also on site (with a hand held potentiostat) for the measurement of total polyphenols in tea in terms of any standard polyphenol (e.g. catechin). The running cost of such sensing system will be negligible compared to other techniques. The sensor would be useful tool to assess the quality of tea for the valuation.

The aim of the present work was the detection of total polyphenols (with respect of catechin family) quantitatively in different green and black tea using different electrodes (such as screen-printed, glassy carbon and platinum electrode). The emphasis was given to address the following issues : (i) stability of electrodes, (ii) limit of detection, (iii) interference with other constituents, (iv) response time.

Results and discussion

Cyclic voltammetric and amperometric measurements :

FeCl_3 oxidizes alcohols to aldehydes (or ketones) and is itself reduced to FeCl_2 ¹⁵. The reaction involves electron transfer between the working electrode and counter electrode when a fixed voltage was applied across reference electrode and thus the response was monitored by amperometry. The redox reaction cycle on the working electrode is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic description of the redox reaction between polyphenols and FeCl_3 .

To identify the optimum oxidation potentials, cyclic voltammograms were run with a scan rate of 0.05 V/s in presence of catechin and distinct peaks were observed. It is clear from Table 1 that the oxidation peak of 0.208 V was characteristic for polyphenols when S1 was used. Hence amperometry was performed at 0.208 V for S1.

Table 1. Comparison of peak voltages obtained from cyclic voltammograms using different electrodes (S1, S2, S3)

Sl. no.	Electrode type	Electrode details	Analyte	Oxidation peak (V)
1.	S1	Screen-printed (with nano carbon tube)	Polyphenols	0.208
2.	S2	WE : glassy carbon, RE : silver, CE : platinum	Polyphenols	0.435
3.	S3	WE : platinum, RE : silver, CE : platinum	Polyphenols	-0.603

The characteristic oxidation peak for the polyphenols was 0.435 V for S2 and -0.603 V when S3 was used. Fig. 2 shows oxidation peak at 0.435 V for S2. Hence with these fixed potential values we performed amperometric study for estimation of TP content of different green and black tea using S1, S2 and S3. Fig. 3 shows the calibration curve for responses of different concentrations of catechin in the range of 0-400 $\mu\text{g/L}$ using above modi-

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram for catechin (200 mg/L) using glassy carbon electrode (S2).

Fig. 3. Comparison between calibration curves for catechin using different electrodes (S1, S2 and S3) : (1) screen printed electrode ($y = 12.247x - 96.527$; $R^2 = 0.9934$); (2) glassy carbon electrode ($y = 2.9702x + 0.8024$; $R^2 = 0.993$); (3) platinum electrode ($y = 32.019x + 124.69$; $R^2 = 0.9925$).

fied electrodes. The TP content of nine tea samples were calculated from the current responses of amperometric measurement using the calibration curve for catechin and expressed in mg catechin/g of tea leaves and presented in Table 2. The mean values and standard deviations are also given in this Table. It could be seen that the green tea had the highest TP while black tea had a significantly lower TP content. This might be due to more fermentation in the latter than the first one. The sensing systems have been checked for interferences for various common agents such as L-phenylalanine, D-fructose, oxalic acid and L-ascorbic acid. The results obtained from the study of interference have been satisfactory since insignificant

Table 2. Total polyphenols (TP) content in different green and black tea samples (mg of catechin/g tea leaves) measured by modified electrodes

Tea sample number	TP content in tea (mg catechin/g of tea leaves)	TP content in tea (mg catechin/g of tea leaves)	TP content in tea (mg catechin/g of tea leaves)
	Screen-printed electrode	Glassy carbon electrode	Platinum electrode
1	7.1 ± 0.5	4.9 ± 0.4	7.6 ± 0.6
2	7.5 ± 0.6	3.7 ± 0.3	7.1 ± 0.7
3	7.2 ± 0.5	5.3 ± 0.4	6.9 ± 0.6
4	6.2 ± 0.6	4.8 ± 0.3	6.6 ± 0.5
5	5.7 ± 0.5	4.7 ± 0.4	5.3 ± 0.5
6	1.5 ± 0.03	0.6 ± 0.03	1.1 ± 0.05
7	0.6 ± 0.03	0.5 ± 0.02	0.8 ± 0.04
8	0.5 ± 0.02	0.3 ± 0.02	0.7 ± 0.04
9	0.8 ± 0.04	0.4 ± 0.03	0.6 ± 0.03

Results represent mean values \pm standard deviation (SD) of three independent measurements.

Fig. 4. Effect of presence of probable interfering substances on response given by modified screen printed electrode (S1) : (1) amino acid (D-phenylalanine), (2) ascorbic acid, (3) carbohydrate (D-fructose), (4) organic acid (oxalic acid).

variations of response were obtained for the interfering substances used which is shown in Fig. 4 (for S1).

Limit of detection and limit of quantification :

The limits of detection (LOD)¹⁶, limit of quantification (LOQ)¹⁶ of FeCl₃ modified different electrodes are given in Table 3. These parameters were calculated following the given expressions :

$$\text{LOD} = 3S/m \tag{1}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10S/m \tag{2}$$

where, m represents the slope of the graph or sensitivity and S is the standard deviation. As the LOD values for screen-printed (S1), glassy carbon (S2) and platinum (S3) electrodes were 0.246 mg/L, 0.192 mg/L and 0.318 mg/L respectively (from Table 3), therefore the sensitivity of the detection was in the order $S2 > S1 > S3$. It might be

Table 3. Limit of detection, limit of quantification values for FeCl₃ modified electrodes

Name of the electrodes	Limit of detection (mg/L)	Limit of quantification (mg/L)
Screen-printed	0.246	0.820
Glassy carbon	0.192	0.640
Platinum	0.318	1.059

recalled that for S1, S2 and S3, currents were measured across carbon-carbon, glassy carbon-glassy carbon and platinum-platinum electrodes respectively. The specific resistance of glassy carbon-glassy carbon (S2) electrodes was the lowest among all the three transducers. S2 and S3 were somewhat costly to manufacture, but can be used

chromatograms at 280 nm corresponding to the individual members of catechin family was calculated and summed up to get TP¹⁷. The HPLC chromatogram of standard (gallic acid and epicatechin), one green tea (sample 4) and one black tea (sample 6) were represented in Fig. 5 (a), (b), (c) and (d) respectively.

Correlation between methods :

A high correlation coefficient was obtained between different electrochemical sensors and HPLC methods. A correlation matrix represented the comparative study of polyphenols (in respect of catechin) for different methods shown in Table 4. The highest correlation index was obtained for total polyphenols estimation by ES(PtE) sensor with ES(SPE) sensor (0.97) whereas lowest correlation showed between ES(GCE) sensor and HPLC (0.74). Correlation between ES(PtE) and HPLC was slightly greater (0.85) than ES(SPE) and HPLC (0.83). The result showed that ES(PtE) and ES(SPE) could be used conveniently for determination of TP content of tea.

Fig. 5. The HPLC chromatogram of standard (a) gallic acid, (b) epicatechin, (c) green tea (sample 4), (d) black tea (sample 6).

number of times, whereas S1 is economical and disposable in nature.

HPLC measurements :

The total polyphenols (TP) contents of investigated tea were determined by comparing with peak areas given by standard solutions of a number of polyphenols in the catechin family. The individual peak area given by HPLC

Table 4. Correlation matrix obtained from responses due to catechin by the proposed electrochemical sensors and standard HPLC method

	ES (SPE)	ES (GCE)	ES (PtE)	HPLC
ES (SPE)	1	0.90	0.97	0.83
ES (GCE)	0.90	1	0.87	0.74
ES (PtE)	0.97	0.87	1	0.85
HPLC	0.83	0.74	0.85	1

Table 5 presents an overall comparison of polyphenol biosensors, developed by several researchers in the recent past (2001-2010)¹⁸⁻²⁴. This work has established improvements on different accounts such as interference, detection limit and stability for qualitative estimation of tea polyphenols.

ration of buffer. All other chemicals were of analytical grade and were purchased from Merck (India). HPLC grade acetonitrile, acetic acid and water for HPLC analysis were purchased from Merck (India).

Samples of green and black tea leaves were collected from market.

Table 5. Comparison of performance of proposed sensors with published reports

Sr. no.	Type of electrodes	Measurement range (mg/L)	Sample	Detection limit (mg/L)	Detector elements	Stability	Interference	Ref.
1.	SAM	Upto 7.5 for catechin	Wine and tea	0.6	HRP	Unstable	No significant effect except sodium hydrogen sulfite	[18]
2.	Carbon paste	0.35 to 17.5 for chlorogenic acid (CGA)	Coffee and mate tea	0.245	HRP	Unstable	No significant effect	[19]
3.	Graphite	1.2 to 12 for catechin	Plant flavonoids	1.308	Laccase	Unstable	-	[20]
4.	Boron-doped diamond (BDD)	0.1 to 47.7 for catechin	Catechin solution	0.04	Ruthenium tris-(2,2')-bipyridyl [Ru(bpy) ₃ ³⁺]	Stable		[21]
5.	O ₂ -type Clark	0.003 to 0.03 for catechin	Tea	-	Tyrosinase	Unstable	-	[22]
6.	Carbon paste	Upto 70.0 for catechin	Tea	1.35	Beta-cyclodextrin	Stable	No significant effect	[23]
7.	Glassy carbon	0.075 to 9 for catechin	Tea	0.02	Polyaspartic acid	Stable	Deviations < 5%	[24]
8.	Screen-printed, glassy carbon, platinum	Upto 400 for catechin	Tea	0.192 to 0.318	FeCl ₃	Stable	No interference	Present work

The response due to addition of tea samples changed with time until 5 min. Hence a time of 5 min was chosen as sensing time.

We performed the stability of modified screen printed electrode where stability faller near 25% after two months. Therefore it is clear that the immobilized electrodes were used for a long time.

Experimental

Reagents :

Ferric chloride and (+)-catechin (≥ 98%, TLC) were purchased from Sigma, UK. Gelatin and glutaraldehyde were obtained from Merck (India). 0.1 (M) of sodium phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) was prepared using di-sodium hydrogen phosphate, dihydrogen sodium phosphate and potassium chloride purchased from Merck (India). Milli-Q (Millipore India Ltd., India) water was used for prepa-

Instrumentation :

Amperometric responses were observed by an Autolab (Ecochemie B.V., The Netherlands) electrochemical analyzer (PGSTAT 12). The terminals of the working (WE), reference (RE) and counter (CE) electrodes of the autolab analyzer were connected to the respective terminals of the transducer via standard connectors and experimental input parameters such as scan rate, potential, time of observation, etc. were applied through general purpose electrochemical software (GPES) from a computer interfaced with the Autolab analyzer.

Sensor fabrication :

Three sensing systems i.e. S1, S2, S3 have been used for the detection of polyphenols. S1 was disposable multi-walled carbon nanotubes modified screen-printed electrode (SPE) [Dropsens C110, USA] having a carbon (4

mm diameter) working electrode, carbon counter electrode and silver reference electrode. The base material used was a ceramic substrate : L33 × W10 × H0.5 mm. The assembly S2 consisted of three electrodes, namely a pseudo-reference (silver, product no. 6.1204.130, length : 52.5 mm, electrode diameter : 2 mm, Metrohm, Switzerland), glassy carbon working electrode (product no. 6.1204.300, length : 52.5 mm, electrode diameter : 3 mm, Metrohm, Switzerland) and a platinum counter electrode (product no. 6.1204.310, length : 52.5 mm, electrode diameter : 3 mm, Metrohm, Switzerland).

The arrangement of S3 was similar to S2 in construction except that the working electrode was made of platinum (product no. 6.1204.310, length : 52.5 mm, electrode diameter : 3 mm, Metrohm, Switzerland) instead of glassy carbon. The arrangement of the electrodes in the experimental set-up for both S2 and S3 is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of S2 and S3 transducers.

Methodology :

To construct calibration curves, all the experiments were carried out with pure catechin [dissolved in reverse osmosis (RO) water]. To study interference due to presence of probable interfering substances, each of the modified electrodes was dipped into phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) and each of interfering substances such as amino acid (L-phenylalanine), carbohydrate (D-fructose), organic acid

(oxalic acid) and ascorbic acid was added and amperometric response monitored.

To determine the stability of modified screen printed electrode, the modified electrodes were stored at room temperature for several months with periodic checking of responses using substrate catechin.

Preparation of tea extract :

Different green and black tea samples (e.g. Green tea : Tetley, Twinings, Japanese, Golden tips, Lipton; Black tea : CTC, Tulip bari, BOPL, Twinings) were collected from the market. These were given identification numbers as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 respectively. 0.1 g of each tea was weighed and taken in a beaker. Five ml of boiling water was poured into the beaker and kept for five minutes. The tea infusion thus prepared, was filtered. The supernatant was used for our electrochemical studies.

Modification of working electrodes by polymer :

Prior to modification of glassy carbon and platinum electrode, these were polished with alumina (Al₂O₃) powder and kept into a beaker containing 1 : 1 water and ethanol in the ultrasonic bath for five minutes to clean the electrodes. After sonication, these were washed by RO water. The working electrodes of S1, S2 and S3 were modified forming a membrane by depositing 4 μL 100 mM FeCl₃ with 4 μL 20% gelatin and 2 μL 12.5% glutaraldehyde and drying for 30 min at room temperature.

Measurement by electrochemical sensor :

Cyclic voltammetric analysis :

Cyclic voltammetry was performed using 200 mg/L catechin solution in 0.1 (M) phosphate buffer solution (PBS, pH 6.8) at a scan rate 50 mV/s with potential range -1.25 V to +1.25 V and step potential 0.00305 V for S1, S2 and S3. Cyclic voltammetry was also repeated for blank [mixture of 5 ml 0.1 (M) phosphate buffer solution and 0.5 ml RO water] with S1, S2 and S3.

Amperometric analysis :

Measurement with electrochemical system : S1

S1 was connected to the electrochemical analyzer by a standard connector and the sensor assembly was dipped into 5 ml PBS in a 10 ml beaker and amperometry was performed at 0.208 V vs Ag/AgCl reference electrode. This constant potential was obtained from cyclic voltammetry study. When equilibration was achieved,

amperometric study was conducted by adding stipulated amount of catechin solution to measure responses in the range 0–400 mg/L. These were utilized to construct the calibration curve so that the amperometric response for any tea sample could be converted in terms of amount of catechin equivalent per gram of dry tea leaves. This might be noted that due to dilution of the analyte concentration by ten times, actual concentration being measured was ten times less and this might be reflected in the values of limit of detection or sensitivity etc. In case of tea samples, once the equilibration was achieved, 0.5 ml of tea solution was added and responses noted 300 s after the addition of tea solution. Each experiment was repeated three times independently. Tea samples were tested for their polyphenol contents following the same procedure.

Measurement with electrochemical system : S2 and S3

The sensor assembly was dipped into 5 ml PBS in a 10 ml beaker and amperometry was performed at constant potential (0.435 V for S2, –0.603 V for S3). The optimum oxidation potentials were determined using cyclic voltammetry. Calibration curve were constructed with pure catechin (0–400 mg/L) at fixed applied potential of 0.435 V for S2 and –0.603 V for S3. Once equilibration was achieved, 0.5 ml of tea infusion was added. Each experiment was repeated thrice independently. The responses were noted at 300 s after the addition of different green and black tea solutions.

HPLC analysis of tea polyphenols content :

The HPLC apparatus consisted of a Varian LC system (USA) equipped with a ProStar 230 solvent delivery module, and a ProStar 330 PDA detector. The separation of phenolic compounds was performed on an OmniSpher C18 column (25 cm × 4.6 mm, Varian, USA) equipped with ChromSep guard-column (1 cm × 3 mm, Varian, USA).

50 mg of tea sample was infused with 10 ml freshly boiled distilled water in a boiling water bath for 10 min. The infusion was filtered through filter paper. The filtrate was treated with equal volume of chloroform. After settling, the chloroform layer was discarded to remove caffeine. This procedure was repeated twice²⁵. The ethyl acetate layer was dispensed in eppendroff tubes and was evaporated overnight at 45 °C. The sample was dissolved in HPLC grade water and injected into the loop of the

instrument for analysis²⁶. The chromatographic conditions were as follows :

Injection volume	: 20 µL
Column	: 5µ-Diamonsil™ C18, 4.6 mm × 250 mm
Temperature	: 40 °C
Mobile phase	: Solvent A : acetonitrile/acetic acid/ water (6 : 1 : 193, v); Solvent B : acetonitrile/acetic acid/ water (60 : 1 : 139, v)
Gradient	: 100% (v) solvent A to 100% (v) solvent B by linear gradient during first 45 min and then 100% (v) sol- vent B till 60 min
Flow rate	: 1 ml min ⁻¹
Detector	: Shimadzu SPD ultraviolet detector, 280 nm

Polyphenol standards (gallic acid, epigallocatechin, (+)-catechin-hydrate, caffeic acid, (–)-epicatechin, catechin-gallate) were used for characterization of the phenolics in tea samples. Stock standard polyphenol solutions were diluted with Milli-Q water to constitute concentration of 20 µg/ml for all the standard polyphenols. The amount of TP was calculated from the peak area of HPLC chromatogram.

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